

Effect of Light on the Interaction of Water and Sodium and Potassium Amalgams (preliminary).

BY

S. S. BHATNAGAR, MATA PRASAD

AND

D. M. MUKERJI.

The action of water on sodium and potassium Amalgams has been studied by Berthelot (Compt. rend., 88, 1108) and Kerp (Zeit. anorg. Chem., 1898, 17, 284). Parker (Trans. Chem. Soc., 1913, 103, 2060) studied the rate of reaction of variously treated waters on Sodium Amalgams and found that the activity is enormously increased by the addition of Hydrogen Peroxide. Muller and Riedel (Zeitsch. Elektrochem., 1920, 26, 104) found that the activity was also accelerated in the presence of iron alloys of Molybdenum, Chromium, etc.

Early investigators have shown that alkali metals emit electrons when they are exposed to ultra-violet light or ordinary visible light. Elster and Geitel discovered in 1894 that liquid alloys of Sodium and Potassium exhibited the property of selective Photo-Electric Effect. They also found that in such cases the number of electrons emitted had a maximum value for a particular frequency of light. Maximum effect in case of potassium occurs at $440\mu\mu$ and at $340\mu\mu$ in case of sodium (*cf.* Hughes' Photo-electricity). The same effect was also observed to take place when the metals were in the colloidal state.

The authors undertook this investigation with a view to examine the behaviour of alkali metals (Sodium and Potassium) under the action of light when they are present in combination with mercury in the Amalgams in the liquid state. To observe any effect that may be produced on exposure to light, the interaction of water and Amalgams in presence of light has been studied on account of its being the simplest and least complex chemical action.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Amalgams experimented upon were liquid Sodium and Potassium Amalgams. They were prepared by the electrolytic method of T. W. Richards (J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1922, 44, 601) and were kept in storing vessel out of contact with air where they did not alter in composition for about a fortnight (*cf.* Bhatnagar, Prasad and Mukerji Surface Tension of Amalgams at the Amalgam-Benzene interface J. I. C. S. 1924, 1, 81); The storing vessel was wrapped in a cloth to protect the Amalgams from exposure to light.

The interaction of water and Amalgams was allowed to take place in an optically correct cell A of quartz. It was fitted with an air-tight rubber stopper through which passed a tube B to add water and a tube C to carry the gas evolved to the burette D where it was collected over water under reduced pressure as shown in the figure.

For each experiment about 3 c. c. of the Amalgam were taken out of the storing vessel in a small tube which was completely covered with black paper to protect the Amalgam from being exposed to light. The Amalgam was poured into the reaction cell A which was immediately closed with a rubber cork. The amount of the Amalgam taken for experiment was quite sufficient to cover the bottom of the reaction cell completely.

The cell was then placed in a thermostat maintained at a constant temperature of 40°C. It was kept immersed in the bath for about 5 minutes to acquire the temperature of the bath before any reaction was started. To allow the passage of light through it to the reaction cell, the thermostat carried glass panes on its sides.

To observe the rate of reaction in the dark, the cell was well covered with black paper and black cloth. Light from carbon arc, giving out rays of wave-lengths varying from $210\mu\mu$ to $700\mu\mu$ was used as the source of light. It was always kept at a fixed distance from the thermostat. Also the reaction vessel was kept at a fixed distance from the side of the thermostat in order that the amount of absorption of rays in their passage through the glass panes and water may be the same in each case. The effective wave-lengths of the arc-light were known by taking a spectrum photograph of the light passing through the same thickness of water and glass as in the experiment by means of an Adam Hilger Spectrograph. It was found that the light of the arc falling on the surface of the reactants comprised of wave-lengths ranging from $366\mu\mu$ to $525\mu\mu$.

5 c. c. of pure distilled conductivity water were added to the reaction vessel through the tube B and the gas evolved was measured in the burette after an interval of every 6 minutes. The temperature and the barometric pressure at which the gas was collected, were noted and the volumes were reduced to N. T. P.

For each different Amalgam the readings were first taken in darkness and then on exposure to arc-light. In the latter case the reaction cell with the Amalgam was kept exposed for 5 minutes before the water was dropped in and the initial observation in the burette was taken. Thus any disturbance due to the expansion of air

of the reaction vessel owing to the heating effect of the arc light was eliminated.

The composition of Amalgams was determined by allowing a known amount of Amalgams to react with water and then titrating the alkali (Sodium or Potassium Hydroxide) with standard solution of Hydrochloric Acid. The quantities of Sodium or Potassium present in the Amalgam were then calculated in grams per cent. of the Amalgam.

The effect of light produced on Amalgams containing varying quantities of Sodium or Potassium has been brought out in the following tables :—

TABLE I.

*Concentration of Sodium in the Amalgam = 0.081
gms. %.*

DARK.		LIGHT.	
Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.	Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.
0.67 c.c.	0.67 c.c.	0.88 c.c.	0.88 c.c.
1.08 "	0.41 "	1.35 "	0.47 "
1.35 "	0.27 "	1.66 "	0.31 "
1.68 "	0.18 "	1.97 "	0.31 "
1.72 "	0.19 "	2.20 "	0.23 "
1.91 "	0.19 "	2.45 "	0.25 "
2.18 "	0.22 "	2.68 "	0.18 "
2.31 "	0.18 "	2.79 "	0.16 "
2.48 "	0.17 "	2.96 "	0.19 "
2.56 "	0.08 "	3.11 "	0.18 "

TABLE II.

Concentration of Sodium in the Amalgam = 0.158 grams %.

DARK.		LIGHT.	
Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.	Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.
0.51 c.c.	0.51 c.c.	0.77 c.c.	0.77 c.c.
0.86 "	0.35 "	1.14 "	0.87 "
1.12 "	0.26 "	1.45 "	0.81 "
1.84 "	0.22 "	1.68 "	0.23 "
1.54 "	0.20 "	1.92 "	0.24 "
1.74 "	0.20 "	2.18 "	0.26 "
1.92 "	0.18 "	2.45 "	0.27 "
2.11 "	0.19 "	2.69 "	0.24 "
2.33 "	0.22 "	2.95 "	0.26 "
2.55 "	0.22 "	3.25 "	0.30 "

TABLE III.

Concentration of Sodium in the Amalgam = 0.214 gms. %.

0.54 c.c.	0.54 c.c.	0.98 c.c.	0.98 c.c.
0.84 "	0.30 "	1.53 "	0.55 "
0.98 "	0.14 "	1.97 "	0.44 "
1.17 "	0.19 "	2.36 "	0.39 "
1.40 "	0.23 "	2.62 "	0.26 "
1.61 "	0.21 "	2.83 "	0.21 "
1.73 "	0.12 "	3.05 "	0.22 "
1.90 "	0.17 "	3.23 "	0.18 "
2.12 "	0.22 "	3.43 "	0.20 "
2.34 "	0.22 "	3.82 "	0.39 "

TABLE IV.

Concentration of Sodium in the Amalgam = 0.311 gms. %.

DARK.		LIGHT.	
Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.	Total volumes of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.
0.46 c.c.	0.46 c.c.	1.37 c.c.	1.37 c.c.
0.83 "	0.37 "	2.17 "	0.80 "
1.21 "	0.38 "	2.84 "	0.67 "
1.64 "	0.43 "	3.46 "	0.62 "
2.04 "	0.40 "	4.08 "	0.57 "
2.29 "	0.25 "	4.27 "	0.24 "
2.50 "	0.21 "	4.46 "	0.19 "
2.76 "	0.26 "	4.76 "	0.30 "
3.02 "	0.27 "	5.09 "	0.33 "
3.31 "	0.29 "	5.38 "	0.24 "

TABLE V.

Concentration of Potassium in the Amalgam = 0.038 gms. %.

0.54 c. c.	0.54 c. c.	0.76 c. c.	0.76 c. c.
0.84 "	0.30 "	1.20 "	0.44 "
1.12 "	0.28 "	1.56 "	0.36 "
1.40 "	0.28 "	1.92 "	0.36 "
1.68 "	0.23 "	2.16 "	0.24 "
1.86 "	0.23 "	2.48 "	0.32 "
2.05 "	0.19 "	2.77 "	0.29 "
2.21 "	0.16 "	3.10 "	0.33 "
2.37 "	0.16 "	3.42 "	0.32 "
2.52 "	0.15 "	3.63 "	0.21 "

TABLE VI.

Concentration of Potassium in the Amalgam = 0.041 gms. %.

DARK		LIGHT	
Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.	Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive interval of 6 minutes.
0.63 c. c.	0.63 c. c.	0.83 c. c.	0.83 c. c.
1.07 "	0.44 "	1.54 "	0.71 "
1.50 "	0.43 "	2.06 "	0.53 "
1.84 "	0.34 "	2.61 "	0.55 "
2.18 "	0.34 "	2.99 "	0.38 "
2.43 "	0.20 "	3.35 "	0.36 "
2.76 "	0.28 "	3.68 "	0.33 "
3.01 "	0.25 "	4.03 "	0.34 "
3.28 "	0.27 "	4.35 "	0.33 "
3.49 "	0.21 "	4.61 "	0.26 "

TABLE VII.

Concentration of Potassium in the Amalgam = 0.056 gms. %.

0.60 c. c.	0.60 c. c.	1.17 c. c.	1.17 c. c.
1.28 "	0.68 "	991 "	0.82 "
1.60 "	0.52 "	2.60 "	0.61 "
2.28 "	0.48 "	3.11 "	0.51 "
2.76 "	0.48 "	3.68 "	0.52 "
3.23 "	0.47 "	4.01 "	0.40 "
3.65 "	0.42 "	4.32 "	0.29 "
3.99 "	0.34 "	4.62 "	0.30 "
4.31 "	0.32 "	4.85 "	0.33 "
4.69 "	0.35 "	5.23 "	0.28 "

TABLE VIII.

Concentration of Potassium in the Amalgam=0.101 gms. %.

DARK		LIGHT	
Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.	Total volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) accumulated at intervals of 6 minutes.	Volume of gas (reduced to N. T. P.) evolved in consecutive intervals of 6 minutes.
0.66 c. c.	0.66 c. c.	1.31 c. c.	1.31 c. c.
1.46 "	0.80 "	3.23 "	0.97 "
2.21 "	0.75 "	3.02 "	0.74 "
2.80 "	0.59 "	3.63 "	0.61 "
3.22 "	0.52 "	4.13 "	0.50 "
3.80 "	0.48 "	4.60 "	0.47 "
4.14 "	0.34 "	5.05 "	0.45 "
4.55 "	0.41 "	5.45 "	0.40 "
4.98 "	0.43 "	5.92 "	0.47 "
5.34 "	0.36 "	6.28 "	0.36 "

Discussion of Results.

It will be seen from the Tables I-VIII that in all cases the rate of evolution of the gas (hydrogen) by the action of Amalgams on water is increased by the presence of light. The total increase in volume of the gas evolved in an hour on change of Sodium and Potassium content of the Amalgam is indicated in the following Tables.

TABLE IX.

Sodium Amalgams.

Quantity of Na in 100 gms. of Amalgam.	Increase in volume of the gas in one hour.
0.081 gms.	0.55 c. c.
0.168 "	0.70 "
0.214 "	1.45 "
0.301 "	2.52 "
0.311 "	20.2 "

TABLE X.

Potassium Amalgams.

Quantity of K in 100 gms. of Amalgam	Increase in volume of the gas in one hour.
0.038 gms.	1.11 c. c.
0.041 "	1.12 "
0.056 "	1.54 "
0.101 "	0.94 "

The above Tables show that the difference in volume of the gas evolved in light and in darkness increases as the amount of Sodium or Potassium in the Amalgam is increased up to a certain point. After that point the difference decreases on further increasing the concentration of Sodium or Potassium. These latter points lie on a different branch of the curve obtained by plotting the amount of Sodium or Potassium in 100 grams of the Amalgam against increase in volume.

Authors, while determining the Interfacial Tension of Sodium and Potassium Amalgams against Benzene, found that these points lay on different straight lines obtained by plotting the quantities of Sodium or Potassium in 100 grams of the Amalgam against interfacial Tensions (*cf.* Bhatnagar and Prasad and Mukerji, *loc. cit.*).

From the foregoing Tables it is clear that the activity of Sodium and Potassium Amalgams is accelerated in the presence of light. This increase in the activity may be due to the emission of electrons by Sodium and Potassium present in the Amalgams. The reaction, according to Einetein (Ann. d. Physik, 1912, (4) 37, 832), Landesberg (Journ, Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc. 1915, 47, 908),

and others, is a photochemical one and it is proposed to investigate it further from the view-point of Einstein's Photochemical equation.

Wiedmann (Ber. d. Deutsch. phys. Gesell, 1916, 18, 333), has found that to produce selective photo-electric effect in Potassium, the presence of Hydrogen gas is essential. Photo-electric effect, whether selective or normal (*cf.* Millikan and Sonder, Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci, 1916, 2, 19), might have been produced in this case by the presence of the Hydrogen gas evolved in the reaction.

The reaction of Amalgams on water takes place in the dark as well, but not to the same extent as in light. It has been pointed out by Baly (Physikal. Zeitsch. 1913, 14, 893), Henri and Würmser (Journ. d. Physique, (5) 1913, 3, 305), that in cases of substances dissolved in a solvent, the reaction is accelerated and not initiated by light. These Amalgams have also been shown to belong to the same category.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,

BENARES HINDU UNIVERSITY,

BENARES, (INDIA).

AND

THE PANJAB UNIVERSITY, LAHORE.
